

THE PERCEPTION OF DEVOTED TEACHING: TEACHER PERSPECTIVES*

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research is to examine the devoted teachers' devoted teacher perceptions. For this purpose, according to the perceptions of teachers in a sense the answer was sought for the question "who is devoted teachers". The research is expected to contribute to the literature in this respect. In this research, screening method was used. In research it was tried to be revealed as the teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching. The universe of the research was composed of teachers working in secondary school and high school. The sample consisted of 355 teachers working in secondary and high school. The research data were collected during the 2016-2017 academic year spring semester. A devoted teacher scale developed by the researchers was used in the research. The scale consists of 37 items with one factor. According to the findings of the research, teachers' devoted teaching perceptions are "always" at the level of 4.29. Teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching do not make a meaningful difference in terms of gender, educational status, branch, school, and graduated faculty. However, teachers' perceptions of devoted teachers vary according to seniority, and according to seniority variable, devoted teachers' perceptions differ significantly. According to the results of the research, teachers perceive themselves as devoted at the "always" level.

Keywords: teacher, devoted teacher, responsibility

1. Introduction

One of the most important variables of the educational institutions is "a teacher". A teacher (or an instructor), in the dictionary of education and psychology, is described as 'a person appointed in a private or state education institution to guide or help students

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find paths to acquire learning experiences'. Another definition in the dictionary is like this: "A teacher is someone who serves or contributes to other people interacting with him grow or develop thanks to his abundant and extraordinary experiences or education, or both, in a certain domain" (Bakircioglu, 2014a). A teacher is the one carrying the world's greatest responsibility, *taking the Man from the cradle to the grave* (Topcu, 2004).

As in all professions, teachers are required to have some professional and personal qualities in order to practice the teaching profession. Since the primary task of teachers is to provide learning, they should have professional qualifications to fulfill this task. The professional nature of the teachers depends on general culture, subject area knowledge and professional teaching knowledge and skills. A teacher, whose primary task is to socialize the student and transfer the social culture, should be familiar with the cultural characteristics of the society in which s/he lives, otherwise; it may come to the point of conflict with the society in which they serve (Erden, 2014). Teacher training programs in our country aims that the teacher candidates have knowledge of a specific area of expertise such as Mathematics teacher, Science teacher, and Turkish teacher. Accordingly, through some of the courses included by curriculums in the faculties of education, it is aimed that teachers will have the knowledge of the subject area. For the professional success of teaching, it is first crucial to know the area of expertise (Şişman, 1999). Besides having expertise in a branch, a teacher also needs some knowledge and skills intricately related to the teaching profession. How well a teacher knows the subject area, s/he cannot succeed in this profession if s/he cannot make students acquire the knowledge of that area. In this regard, a teacher is required to have the ability to provide learning (Erden, 2014).

A lot of research regarding the personal characteristics that teachers should have has been carried out and these studies have emphasized different personality traits. Not to mention the standard personality traits that a good teacher should have today, some of the prominent ones are as follows: being tolerant and patient; being open-minded, flexible and adaptive; being loving, understanding and humorous; being encouraging and supportive; being able to examine the problems about education following scientific methods; to anticipate higher level of success; being fair and altruist, to consider personal differences in education, to be open to innovation and development; to be able to update himself/herself constantly; to understand and interpret the social changes; to respect people's freedom of opinion, religion and conscience; to understand the positive and necessary changes in every institution; and to understand and strive to lower anxiety and tension under all circumstances (Çelikten, Şanal, and Yeni, 2005; Erden, 2014; Taşkaya, 2012; Varış, 1998; Yetim and Göktaş, 2004). As observed, one of the personality traits that teachers should have in the literature is altruism. In fact, professional behaviors in accordance with all these personal characteristics also requires teachers to be altruist.

Devotion, defined as 'unselfish regard for the welfare of others, to give up one's on interests for anything that is sought or for the sake of an end, to give up one's personal wishes, desires and desires' is one of the most important characteristics of the teaching profession such as sacrifice, patience and tolerance (Bakircioglu, 2014b, TDK,

2017). According to Monroe (2002), altruism means action for the sake of others. A teacher dealing with human beings, as biological, psychological and socio-cultural beings, should be friendly, supportive, self-sacrificing, tolerant and patient (Helvacı, 2016). Teaching is a profession which also requires altruism, tolerance, constant update of oneself and love of profession (Girgin ve Baysal, 2005).

Burns and Carpenter (2008) reports that teachers in effective and successful schools should face up to the challenges they experience and continue working unhesitatingly and devotedly in order to be more helpful to their students and to reach the school's goals more effectively and quickly. In the same regard, it is also important for teachers to work in a spirit of 'teamwork, connectedness and volunteerism', self-sacrifice and altruism so that they can contribute to their school more (Bogler and Somech, 2005). Since the teacher pursues his/her career not only in school boundaries but also in every phase or domain in his/her life, it requires the teacher to make sacrifices in terms of biological, psychological and social needs and desires (Yetim and Göktaş, 2004). In 1924, at the congress of Teachers' Association [*Muallimler Birliği*], Atatürk stated that the value of the students as the works of teachers was shaped by the degree of self-sacrifice and altruism of their teachers and emphasized that the new generation would be raised by Republic's dedicated teachers and educators (Ataturk, 1924).

In our education system, hundreds of thousands of teachers work and thousands of novice teachers are added every year. One of the questions to be asked at this point appears to be "*How much of these teachers are conscious of their responsibility?*" While some of the teachers with a sense of responsibility act devotedly, others do not, or cannot, think outside the box. It is observed that the teachers who cannot think beyond certain molds do not make a difference in education, and those devoted teachers aim for the top in success within their contexts.

It seems that it is not possible to talk about equality of opportunity in education properly since there exist various materials, physical and social conditions affecting education in different regions in our country. Indeed, PISA 2015 results revealed that there appears to be extreme differences between the western and eastern regions in Turkey in terms of academic achievement. In mathematical literacy, the region having the highest achievement in Turkey, an average score of 442, is the Aegean region while the region with the lowest achievement level is the Eastern Anatolian Region with an average score of 370. The difference between these two regions is approximately 72 (MEB, 2016). This finding results in that teachers should work harder and sacrifice themselves for students with limited opportunities and facilities to access information. Ferreira and Gignoux (2010), in their report investigating the inequality of opportunity in education in Turkey, found out statistically significant relationships between the presence of schools in the East or rural areas and low test scores according to PISA results, even if other conditions are controlled. The significant variables of the inequality of opportunity in education are gender, socio-economic conditions, the geographical conditions in which students live and the school buildings and the inequalities between individuals in these domains are deepened by the qualifications of

teachers, materials and schools, and this has adversely affected the achievement of students (Mete, 2009; Oakes, 2004). This finding results in that teachers should work harder and sacrifice themselves for students with limited opportunities and facilities to access information.

Many researchers have revealed that teachers need and are expected to be devoted and self-sacrificing in their profession. In their research, Taşkın and Hacıömeroğlu (2010) have pointed out to the qualities which candidate teachers are required to have regarding the student–teacher interaction through the use of the concepts of ‘patience’ and ‘altruism’. Özgan, Bulut, Bulut, and Bozbayındır (2013) concluded in their research that devoted love, intricate components of spiritual leadership, is an important predictor for teachers' motivation. Akıllı and Seven (2010), in their paper to determine their attitudes towards teaching profession, asserted that the participants identified the components of the teaching profession utilizing high-level values such as honor, patience, altruism and self-sacrifice. In his research focusing on the opinion of classroom teachers, who started profession in the past (in 1942) and in 2003, regarding teaching profession, Semerci (2009) came to the conclusion that patience, self-sacrifice, altruism, empathy, frugality, love, respect, tolerance, caring and embracing students were highlighted as personal qualities a teacher should have. As can be inferred between the lines, altruism is one of the qualities teachers should have.

Within this context, the purpose of this research is to examine teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching. In a sense, this paper seeks for an answer to the question "*Who is an devoted teacher?*", according to teachers' perceptions. It is expected to contribute to the literature in this direction. For this purpose, answers to the following questions are sought:

1. What is the level of teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching?
2. Do the teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching significantly differ in terms of gender, education status, branch, school, the faculty graduated and seniority variables?

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This study, which strives to examine teachers' perceptions regarding devoted teachers, utilizes survey model, one of the descriptive research models. Survey models are approaches, which simply attempt to determine, describe or identify “what is” – either in the past or at present (Karasar, 2012). In survey model, it is generally sought findings regarding the current situation of the case or problem the researcher focus on (Çepni, 2007). In survey models, data are gathered at a specific time interval with an intention to explain and explore the nature of the existing conditions or establishing relationships between specific events (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2013). In the survey model, researchers ask questions about people's beliefs, opinions, characteristics, and behaviors (Ary, Jacobs, Irvine, and Walker, 2013). The perception of devoted teachers is attempted to be defined, within the perspectives of the participants, as existed in its own context.

2.2 Population and Sample

The population of the research was comprised of all the teachers working in secondary and high schools in Diyarbakır in 2016-2017 schooling year. The sample of the research, however, included 366 teachers randomly selected out of these schools. Eleven data forms were excluded since they were considered to have either unresponded items or insincere responses. The analyses, in the study, were carried out utilizing the data set obtained through the measurement tool administered to 355 teachers. Table 1 presents demographic findings.

Table 1: The distribution of the participants by demographic variables

Gender	N	%
Female	180	50,7
Male	175	49,3
Total	355	100,0
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Education Level	N	%
Bachelor's Degree	331	93,2
Master's Degree	23	6,5
Ph. D.	1	,3
Total	355	100
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Faculty	N	%
Faculty of Education	274	77,2
Faculty of Science and Letters	66	18,6
Others	15	4,2
Total	355	100
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Seniority	N	%
1-5 yr	125	35,2
6-10 yrs	74	20,8
11-15 yrs	66	18,6
16-20 yrs	42	11,8
20-25 yrs	25	7,0
26 yrs+	23	6,5
Total	355	100,0
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School	N	%
Secondary School	240	67,6
High School	115	32,4
Total	355	100,0
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Teaching Branch	N	%
Maths	63	17,7
Science	77	21,7
Turkish - Literature	57	16,1
Social Studies	81	22,8
Visual Arts – P.E.	38	10,7
Foreign Languages	39	11,0
Total	355	100,0

There were many branches in the survey as variables, but branches were grouped under six categories in terms of ensuring suitability for analyses. These categories were as follows: 'Science' category included Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Science and Technology, and Design Teaching. 'Turkish – Literature' category consisted of Turkish and Literature. 'Social Sciences' category was comprised of History, Geography Philosophy, and Teaching of Religion Culture and Ethics. 'Visual Arts – Physical Education' category was composed of teachers of music, painting and physical education. 'Foreign Languages' category included English and German language teaching branches. 'Others' category under the faculty variable stands for the Faculty of Theology and the School of Physical Education and Sports.

2.3 Data Collection Instrument

The Devoted Teacher Scale, the main data collection tool in the research, was developed by researchers after a thorough survey of national and international literature. For the scale development study, the relevant literature (Çelikten et al., 2005; Stronge, Tucker, and Hindman, 2004; Klassen, Yerdelen and Durksen, 2013; Kilimci, 2011; Erden, 2014; Fernet, Sénécal, Guay, Marsh and Dowson, 2008; Özkan, 2017; Şişman, 2016; Sünbül, 2015) was examined. In addition, 20 teachers were asked to write their opinions about the devoted teachers. A 52 – item pool was created after these steps. In order to ensure the content validity of the item pool, five experts in the field were asked for opinion and the 46-item trial form was finalized. A 5-point Likert scale was utilized to determine the level of competence, regarding the items [Never: 1; Rarely: 2; Sometimes: 3; Most of the time: 4; Always: 5].

The 46-item trial form was then administered in a pilot study and exploratory factor analysis was carried out using the obtained data set. Within the context of exploratory factor analysis, KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Test for Sampling Adequacy) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, which test and indicate the suitability of the data for analyses, were examined. KMO value was calculated as .939 and the Bartlett test value was significant (.000). These values indicate that the data set was appropriate and suitable for the factor analysis (Büyüköztürk, 2010; Seçer, 2013). Items having the factor loading values below .50, a total of 9 items, were excluded from the measurement tool, during the analyses. Since the items cannot be grouped under certain themes, as the scree plot indicated, it was concluded that the scale is a one-factor scale, consisting of 37 items. The total variance explained by the single factor was observed to be 38%. It is regarded appropriate and suitable if the total variance explained on single factor scales is 30% or more (Büyüköztürk, 2010). Cronbach Alpha coefficient of internal consistency for the overall scale was .95. This suggests that the scale seems to be highly reliable (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994).

2.4 Data Collection

The data collection instrument was administered to teachers working in secondary and high schools in Diyarbakır between March 15 – April 15 in 2016-2017 schooling year. Before the scale administration in the study, participants were informed about the

purpose of the research, how to respond to scale, and only volunteers were asked to participate in the research. The scale was applied in a way not to interfere with the teaching process and the average response time of the scale was approximately 10-15 minutes. Overall, 366 forms returned, and the analyses were continued using data based upon 355 forms, since eleven of those were not considered as appropriate and were excluded.

2.5 Data Analysis

The SPSS Statistics 22 software was used to analyze the data. First, it was checked whether the distribution meets the normality assumption or not, in order to determine which types of tests to utilize. In cases the normality assumption was met were used parametric tests (Independent Samples T-Test, One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)) were used in the analyses. The 5-point Likert-type scale points and the score ranges were evaluated as follows:

Table 2: Likert-Type Scale Points and Score Intervals

Always	4.20 - 5.00
Often	3.40 - 4.19
Sometimes	2.60 - 3.39
Rarely	1.80 - 2.59
Never	1.00 - 1.79

3. Findings

This section presents findings from research data in accordance with the research questions. Findings regarding the first research problem, namely 'What is the level of teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching?', are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Scale Average Points Regarding Teachers' Perceptions of Devoted Teaching

N	$\bar{X}$	SD
355	4,29	,480

When we look at the mean scores obtained in the scale ($\bar{X}=4,29$), it is observed that the perceptions of devoted teaching appear to be at the "Always" level. Findings regarding the second research question, "*Do the teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching significantly differ in terms of gender variable?*", are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Independent Samples T-Test Results Regarding Teachers' Perceptions of Devoted Teaching by Gender

Gender	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	t	p
Female	180	4,29	,48326	353	0.307	,759
Male	175	4,28	,47908			

Independent samples t-test carried out to test whether the teachers' perception of devoted teaching differed significantly in terms of gender variable yielded findings to

indicate that the difference between groups is insignificant ($t(353) = 307, p > .05$). This may be concluded that gender is not a variable that affects teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching. It can be inferred that male teachers' mean scores of devoted teaching ($\bar{X}=4,28$) and female teachers' average deductive teaching point average ($\bar{X}=4,29$) are almost the same.

Findings regarding the third research question, “Do the teachers’ perceptions of devoted teaching significantly differ in terms of education level variable?”, are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Independent Samples T-Test Results Regarding Teachers' Perceptions of Devoted Teaching by Education Level

Education Level	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	t	p
Bachelor’s Degree	331	4,2946	,48384	353	0.383	,702
Graduate Degree	24	4,2556	,44108			

Independent samples t-test carried out to test whether the teachers' perception of devoted teaching differed significantly in terms of education level variable yielded findings to indicate that the difference between groups is insignificant ($t(353)=.383, p>.05$). Accordingly, it can be concluded that the education level appears to be a factor not affecting teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching. According to Table 5, the mean score of teachers holding a graduate degree is $\bar{X}=4,25$ while the teachers holding a bachelor degree have mean score of $\bar{X}=4,29$.

Findings regarding the fourth research question, “Do the teachers’ perceptions of devoted teaching significantly differ in terms of teaching branch variable?”, are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: One-Way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) Results Regarding Teachers' Perceptions of Devoted Teaching by Teaching Branch

Teaching Branch	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	F	p
Maths	63	4,20	,61525	353	1,43	,563
Science	77	4,29	,520”19			
Turkish - Literature	57	4,34	,47793			
Social Studies	81	4,35	,31519			
Visual Arts – P.E.	38	4,26	,44545			
Foreign Languages	39	4,35	,40852			

One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test carried out to determine whether the teachers' perception of devoted teaching differed significantly in terms of teaching branch variable yielded findings to indicate that the difference among groups is insignificant [$F(353)=1,43, p>.05$]. This illustrates that teaching branch does not have a significant effect on teachers’ perception of devoted teaching.

Findings regarding the fifth research question, “Do the teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching significantly differ in terms of school variable?”, are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Independent Samples T-Test Results Regarding Teachers' Perceptions of Devoted Teaching by School Variable

School	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	t	p
Secondary School	240	4,3010	,45439	353	0.512	,629
High School	115	4,2731	,53274			

Independent samples t-test carried out to test whether the teachers' perception of devoted teaching differed significantly in terms of school variable yielded findings to indicate that the difference between groups is insignificant ($t(353)=.512$, $p>.05$). Hence, the type or level of school the teachers currently work seems to be a factor that does not significantly affect teacher perceptions of devoted teaching.

Findings regarding the sixth research question, "Do the teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching significantly differ in terms of the faculty variable?", are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Independent Samples T-Test Results Regarding Teachers' Perceptions of Devoted Teaching by Faculty Variable

Faculty	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	F	p
Faculty of Education	274	4,28	,4673	353	,968	,552
Faculty of Science and Letters	66	4,33	,5672			
Others	15	4,32	,2709			

One-Way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) carried out to find out whether the teachers' perception of devoted teaching differed significantly in terms of the faculty variable yielded findings to indicate that the difference among groups is insignificant [$F(353)=.968$, $p>.05$]. Accordingly, teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching are not affected by the faculty they graduated.

Findings regarding the fourth research question, "Do the teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching significantly differ in terms of seniority variable?", are presented in Table 9.

Table 9: One-Way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) Results Regarding Teachers' Perceptions of Devoted Teaching by Seniority

Seniority	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	F	p	Sig.
1-5 yrs	125	4,33	,41379	354	3,146	,009	A-C
6-10 yrs	74	4,29	,44177				--
11-15 yrs	66	4,14	,56553				C-E,C-F
16-20 yrs	42	4,20	,63797				D-E,D-F
20-25 yrs	25	4,46	,35486				--
26 yrs +	23	4,48	,32230				--

A: 1-5 yrs, B: 6-10 yrs, C: 11-15 yrs, D: 16-20 yrs, E: 20-25 yrs, F: 26 yrs +

One-Way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) carried out to find out whether the teachers' perception of devoted teaching differed significantly in terms of the seniority variable yielded findings to indicate that the difference among groups is statistically significant

[$F(353)=3,146, p<.05$]. Tukey test, one of the multiple comparison tests, as a post hoc test, was preferred to find out between which groups there is a significant difference. Findings reveal that there exists a significant difference between the mean scores of teachers having seniority of 1-5 years and teachers having seniority of 11-15 –in favor of teachers having seniority of 1-5 years–, teachers having seniority of 11-15 years and teachers having seniority of 21-25 and 26 years –in favor of teachers having seniority of 21-25 and 26 years–, and teachers having seniority of 16-20 years and teachers having seniority of 21-25 and 26 years –in favor of teachers having seniority of 21-25 and 26 years.

4. Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

This section includes and presents results, discussions and suggestions based on the findings of the research.

According to research findings, teachers perceive themselves self-sacrificing at "Always" level. In their research aiming to determine principals' views on "the values teachers should have", Çubukçu, Özenbaş, Çetinkaya, Derya, and Şeker (2012) found that school administrators regarded 'being self-sacrificing' and 'tolerance' as the utmost values that a teacher should have. Togay (2015) concluded in his research that the teacher's commitment was significantly predicted by the 'vision', 'self-sacrifice' and 'spiritual life' variables. Çam (2009), in his research focusing on how supervisors perceive "teachers" and "supervisors" and what attributes they attribute to them, concluded that supervisors attributed most to 'being self-sacrificing - devoted' among the qualities teachers should personally have. According to the results obtained from research findings, there is no significant effect of gender variable on teachers' devoted teaching perceptions. Teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching for male and female teachers are almost at the same level.

In terms of the education level variable, there is no significant difference, indicating that perceptions of devoted teaching by teachers holding a graduate degree and those holding a bachelor's degree do not change significantly. Another result in this research is that teachers' branches do not have a significant effect on their perception of devoted teaching. There is no significant difference in teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching, in terms of the school variable. In other words, the school type, secondary schools or high schools, the participants currently work does not significantly affect their perception of devoted teaching. Findings regarding the faculty variable indicate that the fact that teachers graduated from Faculty of Education, Faculty of Science and Letters, Faculty of Theology and School of Physical Education and Sports does not have a significant effect on their perception of devoted teaching. According to the research findings, teachers' perceptions of devoted teaching are significantly different in terms of the seniority variable. In terms of seniority, teachers having seniority of 20 – 25 and 26 years, which can be regarded as '*the veterans*', report a quite high level of perception while teachers having seniority of 11 – 15 years have a lower level of perception of devoted teaching than the other groups.

The educational opportunities in our country vary across regions. Especially in the eastern and southern provinces, educational achievement appears to be quite low. According to the statistics, it is observed that twenty provinces having the lowest achievement rates in the province rankings in the national selection examinations are in the eastern or south-eastern regions (İlhan and Keskin, 2011). Teachers have the most important duty and responsibility to minimize this difference.

It is thought that if teachers sacrifice themselves and do something beyond defined tasks while teaching, this will develop a positive sense to their students, who take teachers as their role models.

Within this context, a number of recommendations regarding devoted teacher training process have been made to the academicians in the field of teacher education, the education politicians, the practitioners and researchers:

- In courses such as ‘Collective Service Applications’, ‘Teaching Practice’ and ‘School Experience’, generally in authentic school contexts, prospective teachers should be provided sufficient and appropriate vocational guidance about how to act devotedly during difficulties encountered in schools
- The fact that prospective teachers take ‘Teaching Practice’ and ‘School Experience’ courses partly in schools in disadvantaged regions may offer ‘a realistic experience and opportunity’ in preparing them for devoted teaching. The statistics reports in recent years indicate that most teachers were appointed to work in schools far away from the provincial centres in the eastern and south-eastern regions in Turkey. The disadvantages of such regions, such as lack of physical and social facilities, can be inferred from the educational statistics. (MEB, 2016). Hence, preparing the prospective teachers for the profession under realistic and authentic conditions may allow them to gain experience in this respect to act devotedly by partially reducing the problems they will have at the beginning of their professional career.
- Different types of research on teachers' self-sacrifice can be carried out. Especially qualitative research involving observation can contribute to the description of this case. Additionally, multidisciplinary and multiphase research can be done by the participation of various stakeholders such as school principals, students and parents.
- Teachers should be presented or provided example figures of devoted teachers and instructors during their training period.

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Appendix A

The Devoted Teacher Scale

	Items
1	I answer the questions asked by the students without hesitation.
2	I care students' problems not related to the course.
3	I encourage my students to explain their ideas freely.
4	It makes me happy to spend extra time for my students.
5	I support my students' plans.
6	I support my students' personality development.
7	Even at my personal time, I can help a student who wants help.
8	I enjoy having time for students.
9	I try to improve myself constantly to help the students better.
10	It makes me happy to exhibit devoted behaviours.
11	I like to take care of the problems of the learners.
12	I guide the students in acquiring national and spiritual values.
13	Even in difficult conditions, I try to make the student acquire something.
14	I take into account the interests and needs of my students during the learning-teaching process.
15	I make every student feel he/she is special.
16	I make effort to make each student feel special.
17	I believe that devotion is an important characteristic of the teaching profession.
18	I self-criticize myself about the failures of the students.
19	I try to communicate with the students outside the class as well.
20	I believe that teaching is a sacred profession.
21	If necessary, I do not expect any compensation for my teaching.
22	I encourage my colleagues to act devotedly to the student.
23	I believe that the teacher is alone with his conscience in class.
24	I often casuistry about my own profession.
25	It makes me happy if the students are happy.
26	I try hard to transform the learning-teaching process into an authentic interaction environment.
27	During the learning-teaching process, I value the cultural values that students have.
28	Teaching is a lifestyle for me.
29	I enjoy guiding learning.
30	I value my relationship with my colleagues.
31	I take pleasure in helping my colleagues.
32	I care about the problems of my colleagues.
33	I attach importance to the feelings of the students during the teaching-learning process.
34	I constantly try to improve myself through self-assessment.
35	I like doing different activities to create a better teaching-learning process.
36	I take care of the school's problems.
37	I act responsibly to environmental problems.

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